

Milestone: M1.2 Stakeholder Coordination Group portal goes live

Lead Participant: EATRIS

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Due: 31 Jan 2021

Date Of Completion: 19 Oct 2020

Means of Verification

<https://b1mg-project.eu/news-events/>

<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSfDRtFrsYIikOjz0343Rub4F-74foqt8MZJFXsFg1iVyMGc2w/viewform>

Milestone Delayed (if yes, please explain)

No

Problems encountered & solutions recommended: NA

Project participants & others

Emanuela Oldoni (WP1)
Toni Andreu (WP1)
Juan Arenas (WP6)
Denis Horgan (WP1)
Chiara Bernini (WP1)
Ruben Kok (WP1)

Next action steps

- To work with Communications Team to improve the portal
- To engage the Stakeholders group through the Stakeholder portal
- To collect and review stakeholder registrations and give them the portal access
- Portal management

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